

THE EFFECTS OF MATRIX MICROSTRUCTURE AND TEXTURE ON TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF AN "ORTHORHOMBIC" Ti-ALUMINIDE/SiC COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Although the occurrence of microstructural and crystallographic textures in metallic alloys is well known, there is little information concerning the influence of matrix alloy texture on the processing and deformation characteristics of metal matrix composites (MMCs). Texture effects can be especially important in MMCs based on anisotropic matrices such as titanium alloys. This paper deals with the role of matrix alloy microstructure and texture in the tensile behavior of a SiC fiber reinforced "orthorhombic" titanium aluminide composite which was processed by the foil-fiber-foil technique. The results demonstrate that both processing and mechanical behavior of this MMC are markedly affected by matrix anisotropy.

INTRODUCTION

There is extensive research on titanium based metal matrix composites incorporating high strength and high modulus SiC fibers as continuous reinforcement due to their improved specific properties and potential high temperature applications. Numerous studies dealing with the development of composite constituents, processing and behavior of titanium matrix composites have been reported and these have been reviewed elsewhere [1]. While the work on matrix alloy development has considered important issues such as matrix microstructure, fiber/matrix interactions and performance under operating conditions, little attention has been paid to the influence of matrix alloy texture on composite behavior. The occurrence of pronounced deformation and recrystallization textures in conventional titanium alloys has been well documented. Significant textures can also develop in the titanium based composite matrices depending on the processing steps used. The present work reports on the effects of matrix alloy microstructure and texture on the tensile behavior of a titanium aluminide based composite which was consolidated by the foil-fiber-foil method.

Several titanium aluminide alloys containing α_2 (Ti₃Al; DO19), O (Ti₂AlNb; orthorhombic) and β_0 (ordered β ; B2) phases are being investigated for use as matrices of continuously reinforced titanium composites [2, 3]. Previous studies have demonstrated several advantages of an orthorhombic-based alloy, with a nominal composition of Ti-22Al-23Nb (at.%), over the α_2 -based alloy, Ti-24Al-11Nb, when reinforced with SCS-6 SiC fibers [2]. These advantages include reduced fiber/matrix reaction, higher specific strength, creep resistance, and fracture resistance. Since the density of these titanium aluminides increases with increasing Nb level, other matrix alloys having intermediate Nb concentrations between Ti-24Al-11Nb and Ti-22Al-23Nb are also being investigated. The Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix composition used in this study was previously developed as a monolithic alloy with improved toughness and a good balance of properties [4]. More recent work has suggested that the quaternary addition of Mo to this class of titanium aluminide alloys leads to the stabilization of the orthorhombic phase [5].

The objective of this work was to study the effects of microstructure and texture on the tensile behavior of Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo unreinforced matrix and SCS-6 fiber reinforced composite materials which were consolidated using matrix alloy foils.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Uniaxially reinforced 4-ply Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 composite panels containing 35 vol.% SCS-6 fibers were fabricated by Textron Specialty Materials using the foil-fiber-foil technique. The foils used for MMC processing were 125 μm thick and were obtained by unidirectional cold rolling of matrix alloy sheets. Preforms containing alternate layers of matrix alloy foils and fiber mats, with fibers oriented along the foil rolling direction, were consolidated by HIP'ing at 980°C. Unreinforced panels of the alloy were also fabricated under identical processing conditions. The consolidation of all the HIP'd panels was checked nondestructively using radiography and ultrasonic C-scans.

Tensile tests were conducted on unreinforced alloy and composite specimens over the temperature interval 25°C-760°C in air using a nominal strain rate of $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Specimens with longitudinal as well as transverse orientations (with respect to the fiber axis or foil rolling direction) were tested. The characterization of tested specimens included fractography, metallography of longitudinal sections below the fracture surface, and microstructural analysis using optical microscopy, SEM and electron microprobe techniques. The volume fractions of the constituent phases were analyzed using an image analysis program in which an optical density slice function was applied to stored digital SEM images.

Texture measurements were made on the starting alloy foil and unreinforced matrix panel using an automated pole figure diffractometer equipped with a solid state power supply and a lithium drifted silicon detector providing excellent energy resolution. X-ray step scanning was conducted in the plane of the samples using Cu K_{α} radiation to identify the diffraction lines of interest. Pole figure data were taken by positioning the sample at the appropriate 2θ angle for the desired reflection and moving it about the other two axes to determine the intensities of the (hkl) plane at angles with respect to the surface normal. A judicious choice of the diffraction lines was required for performing the texture analysis because of peak overlapping stemming from the large number of diffraction peaks from the β_0 , α_2 and O phases. The instrument was computer controlled and the data for each pole figure were digitally acquired. The popLA texture analysis package was used for quantitatively analyzing the texture data [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows back-scattered electron micrographs from longitudinal and transverse sections of a Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix panel. It should be noted that these section orientations are designated relative to the rolling direction of the alloy foils used for consolidating the panels. The dark, bright and intermediate contrast features in these micrographs correspond to the α_2 , β_0 and O phases, respectively. The O phase appears to form a continuous network with discontinuous regions of coarse α_2 and finer β_0 laths. The volume fractions of the various phases present in this matrix were measured to be 39% α_2 , 43% O and 18% β_0 . A comparison of the longitudinal and transverse sections indicates that the microstructure of the unreinforced Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo panel is strongly textured, i.e. the α_2 grains and the (β_0 +O) two-phase regions are elongated parallel to the rolling direction, but have an equiaxed morphology in sections normal to the rolling direction.

Figure 2 depicts an x-ray scan of a Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo foil showing the three phase microstructure with the O phase diffraction peaks shaded. The characterization of crystallographic texture of this material involved the determination of pole figures for various crystallographic planes in the constituent phases. The basic texture for the β_0 phase was found to be the usual bcc rolling texture of $(100)\langle 011 \rangle$ plus a moderate (111) component in the plane of the sheet with a mild tendency to align in the transverse direction. For the α_2 phase, the basal plane (0001), first order prism plane (01 $\bar{1}$ 0), second order prism plane (11 $\bar{2}$ 0) and the (011 $\bar{2}$) pyramidal plane pole figures were acquired. The (11 $\bar{2}$ 0) pole figure showed the second order

Fig. 1 - SEM back-scattered electron micrographs from unreinforced Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix panel: (a) Longitudinal section, (b) transverse section and (c) a higher magnification image from the longitudinal section. The thickness direction is vertical in these micrographs.

Fig. 2 - X-ray scan of Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo alloy foil showing a three-phase microstructure with O phase diffraction peaks shaded

prism planes lying in the plane of the sheet and at $\pm 60^\circ$ to this plane and aligned along the rolling direction. This was confirmed by the first order prism planes lying at $\pm 30^\circ$ in the (01 $\bar{1}0$) pole figure. Based on this analysis, it was concluded that the α_2 phase hexagonal unit cells lie in the plane of the sheet with their c-axis aligned along the transverse direction (Fig. 3). The results showed that the α_2 phase in the Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix panel is strongly textured ($\sim 11X$ random). The crystallographic texture was less pronounced for the O phase. The measurements showed that it is moderately textured having $\sim 5X$ random (100) bull's eye pole figure. Further, processing of the foils into matrix panels slightly reduced the texture for all the phases.

Fig. 3 - Schematic showing the orientation of α_2 phase hexagonal unit cell in the Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo alloy foil. The arrows RD, TD and ND refer to foil rolling, transverse and normal directions, respectively.

The tensile stress-strain data for the unreinforced Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix at various test temperatures is plotted for longitudinal and transverse specimen orientations in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. The tensile stress-strain curves for specimens loaded along the longitudinal direction (Fig. 4) illustrate the high ductility of the matrix in this orientation at room temperature as well as higher temperatures. In contrast, the specimens loaded along the transverse direction exhibit very poor ductility at 25°C and 593°C. These specimens failed within the elastic region and fracture occurred at or near the grip regions. It appears that the poor strength values obtained for the transverse specimens tested at 593°C resulted from premature failure due to stress concentration at or near the grips. The modulus of the matrix alloy in the transverse direction was

Fig. 4 - Tensile stress-strain behavior of unreinforced Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix in the longitudinal orientation, at various temperatures

Fig. 5 - Tensile stress-strain behavior of unreinforced Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix in the transverse orientation, at various temperatures

~1.5 times that in the longitudinal direction at each of the test temperatures. Further, the test data at 760°C (Fig. 5) indicated that the tensile strength along the transverse direction is more than 1.5 times that in the longitudinal direction at this temperature.

Ultrasonic C-scans of Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 composite indicated the presence of defects at a number of locations within the panels. Some of these defects appeared to be related to fiber-fiber contacts resulting from fiber movement during consolidation. Figure 6(a) shows fiber distribution in a transverse section. A reaction zone measuring ~1.2 μm was observed around the fibers. The fiber/matrix region also showed some cracks within the reaction zone and across surrounding α_2 grains as shown in Fig. 6 (b, c).

Fig. 6 - SEM micrographs of as-consolidated Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 composite sample showing (a) fiber distribution and (b, c) cracks in the reaction zone and adjoining α_2 grains

Fig. 7 - Axial tensile stress-strain behavior of Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 [0]4 composite, at various temperatures

The axial tensile behavior of Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 [0]4 composite specimens at different temperatures is shown in Fig. 7. These specimens exhibited low strain to failure values (0.6 to 0.8%) at all test temperatures. The composite strength values were also low (less than 1200 MPa).

Figures 8(a) and 8(b) show fractographs of Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 [0]4 composite tensile specimen tested at RT and 593°C, respectively. A transverse section below the fracture surface of a [0]4 tensile specimen tested at 760°C is shown in Fig. 9. These results showed many cracks in the matrix which propagated radially between fibers in a zig-zag manner across the panel thickness. Some matrix cracking was also noticed between adjacent fibers within a ply along the bond line of the alloy foils (Fig. 9), especially in regions where the fibers were either very closely spaced or touching each other. Further, the specimens which were tested at the higher temperatures also showed many regions of fiber/matrix debonding.

Fig. 8 - SEM fractographs of Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 [0]4 composite tensile specimens tested at (a) RT and (b) 593°C

Fig. 9 - Optical micrograph from a transverse section below the fracture surface of a Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 [0]4 composite tensile specimen tested at 760°C

The anisotropy of tensile behavior observed for the unreinforced Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix may be explained on the basis of the texture of α_2 phase alone. With the α_2 phase texture as outlined above, it is possible for multiple slip systems to operate under longitudinal loading. However, there is a lack of availability of slip systems under transverse loading conditions since the slip vectors are normal to the loading direction. These implications of the texture analysis are consistent with the results of tensile tests (Figs. 4 and 5). It appears that this difference in the two loading directions persists at temperatures up to 593°C. Above this temperature, additional slip systems become active even in the transverse direction as indicated by the behavior at 760°C (Fig. 5).

The present results also showed that the high ductility of the matrix alloy in the longitudinal direction alone is not a sufficient condition for achieving high axial tensile strengths in the [0]4 composite. The metallographic evaluation of the as-consolidated composite showed some cracking of the fiber/matrix reaction zone as well as the adjacent matrix region. It is suggested that these cracks are formed due to a lack of accommodation of residual hoop stresses in the composite after cooling down from the consolidation temperature. This is consistent with the negligible plasticity of the matrix in the transverse direction at ambient and moderately high temperatures (Fig. 5). It may also be argued that tensile loading of the [0]4 composite specimens containing these matrix cracks results in further growth of these cracks due to Poisson contraction of the matrix around the fibers. An additional factor contributing to the poor tensile properties of the [0]4 composite specimens tested at 593°C and higher temperatures (Fig. 7) is the fiber/matrix interfacial debonding resulting from matrix cracking as shown in Figs. 8 and 9.

SUMMARY

This study deals with the role of matrix microstructure and texture in composite behavior. The Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo unreinforced matrix alloy displayed a pronounced microstructural texture with elongated α_2 grains and (O+ β_0) regions parallel to the rolling (longitudinal) direction of the alloy foils used for consolidation. Crystallographic texture analysis using pole figure measurements revealed that the α_2 phase in the Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo unreinforced matrix panel is strongly textured (~11X random) with the hexagonal unit cells lying in the plane of the panel with their first order prism planes at $\pm 30^\circ$ with the plane of the panel and their c-axis aligned with the transverse direction of the panel. The crystallographic textures of O and β_0 phases were less pronounced. The tensile properties of unreinforced Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo matrix were observed to be anisotropic, with a high ductility in the longitudinal direction and poor ductility in the transverse direction. This anisotropic tensile behavior may be explained on the basis of the texture of the α_2 phase alone. With the aforementioned texture, multiple slip systems of α_2 phase can operate under longitudinal loading and give rise to the ductility observed in this direction. However, there is a lack of availability of slip systems under transverse loading

conditions. This explains the essentially elastic behavior of the alloy in the transverse direction at RT and moderately higher temperatures.

The main result of this work is that the matrix texture can significantly affect the processing and properties of the MMC. In spite of the high ductility of the alloy in the longitudinal direction, the Ti-24.5Al-17Nb-1Mo/SCS-6 [0]4 composite specimens exhibited poor properties with low values of strain to failure (<0.8%) and tensile strength (<1200 MPa). It is suggested that these poor properties are due to damage in the composite following consolidation, arising from matrix anisotropy. As-consolidated composite panels showed radial cracks at the reaction zone and adjoining α_2 grains. These cracks were attributed to a lack of accommodation of residual hoop stresses following processing which is a consequence of lack of plasticity in the transverse direction. Tensile loading of the [0]4 composite specimens resulted in crack growth in the matrix between adjacent fiber plies as well as along the bond lines of the foils. Fiber/matrix interfacial debonding stemming from the matrix cracks also contributed to damage at the higher test temperatures.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was performed at the Wright Laboratory Materials Directorate under AF Contract F33615-91-C-5663. The assistance of Mr. D. Knapke of UDRI in mechanical testing and Mr. W. A. Houston of UES, Inc., in metallographic specimen preparation is acknowledged.

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